

Synthesis of Hollow Spherical Phosphide Catalysts with Industrial-Scale Potential for Alkaline Hydrogen Evolution Reaction

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Abstract

The competitiveness of hydrogen as a fuel of the future relies on the development of low-cost, readily available, and efficient catalysts. Transition metal phosphides, mainly in multimetallic compositions, are recognized as an excellent alternative to platinum-based catalysts in electrolyzers and fuel cells. Herein, for the first time, the connection of the Spray Drying Method as a user-friendly technique for large-scale production of transition metal phosphides as HER catalysts is presented. Three types of catalysts based on MoFeP modified with Co and Ni as third elements were compared by electrochemical methods in an alkaline medium 1M KOH. Among the studied materials, the as-prepared MoFeCoP electrocatalysts exhibited the lowest reaction overpotentials (η_{10}) of -285 mV, with Tafel slopes of 83 mV dec⁻¹ with sufficient durability in long-term stability tests. The high value of differential capacitance for both trimetallic materials MoFeNiP and MoFeCoP indicates a large surface area, which leads

to low activation energy for HER resulting in excellent features for hydrogen production and application.

1. Introduction

The increase in global energy demand is driven by a number of socio-economic factors, such as population growth, urbanization, industrial progress, the development of new technologies and rising net capital income. This is expected to continue to grow rapidly, with demand potentially doubling by 2050. Global dependence on fossil fuels as a primary energy source poses significant environmental and health risks due to greenhouse gas emissions [1]. As readily available fossil fuel reserves dwindle, their extraction is becoming increasingly difficult and expensive.

Hydrogen is an efficient energy carrier and storage medium with numerous benefits. A key advantage is its suitability for long-term storage in practically unlimited amounts. Through electrolysis, excess renewable energy can be used to produce hydrogen gas, allowing for efficient and sustained storage with minimal energy loss. This provides a scalable solution to address the intermittent nature of renewable energy sources [2]. In general, electrochemical water splitting (Eq. 1), as a non-spontaneous process, is driven by the application of electrical energy. It proceeds as two half-reactions: the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) and the oxygen evolution reaction (OER).

Under alkaline conditions, hydroxide anions produced by reductive decomposition of water at the cathode (Eq. 2) are transported towards the anode, where they are oxidized to O_2 (Eq. 3).

Within electrolysis technologies, four common methods are currently known: Alkaline Water Electrolysis (AWE), Anion Exchange Membrane (AEM) Electrolysis, Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) Electrolysis and Solid Oxide Electrolysis (SOEC). Among these, AWE remains the most advanced and historically the most reliable, cost-effective, and mature technology for large-scale hydrogen production [3]. Despite the maturity, robustness and

worldwide deployment, it has severe limitations. The most important ones are low flexibility of operation and inefficient operation at low current densities. Therefore, ongoing research is focused on addressing these issues. One of the investigated approaches allowing improvement of the process performance parameters is the application of new electrode materials with superior catalytic activity and stability. This can be achieved through regulated composition, morphology and nanostructure. Such catalysts could significantly reduce overpotential and enhance the long-term electrocatalytic stability and kinetics of overall water electrolysis. [4], [5].

In recent years, transition metal phosphides (TMP) have been confirmed as promising alternatives to costly precious metal-based electrocatalysts with strong electrocatalytic activity [6]. The enhanced electrocatalytic activity of Transition Metal Phosphides (TMP) for HER is attributed to the abundant catalytically active sites and the synergistic effect of phosphorus and metallic atoms, which optimize the electronic structure of the surface, providing suitable free adsorption energy of key intermediates [6], [7]. Additionally, TMP based on nickel (Ni) exhibits multielectron orbitals that attract protons and possess metalloid properties due to the delocalized electron cloud from Ni-Ni metallic bonds. The presence of phosphorus atoms (P) introduces ionic bonds ($\text{Ni}^{\delta+}-\text{P}^{\delta-}$), which facilitate hydrogen release and enhance stability and resistance in both acidic and highly alkaline environments. Furthermore, Ni_xP_y materials have the ability to expose more unsaturated surface atoms, offering increased catalytic potential [7].

Hang et al. compared the electrochemical performance of five typical monometallic TMPs (Ni_xP_y , Co_xP_y , Mo_xP_y , W_xP_y and Fe_xP_y) at different degrees of phosphorization and with different nanostructures [8]. It is clear from the review that phosphorus content, crystallinity and morphology have an important influence on HER activity. The comparison shows that Ni_xP_y and Co_xP_y exhibit good electrocatalytic performance. For example, Ni_{12}P_5 nanoneedles with lower phosphorus content achieve in 1.0 M KOH an overpotential of -59 mV at η_{-10} [9] while porous CoP nanoparticles show an overpotential of -35 mV at η_{-10} [10] in 1.0 M KOH, but their stability is not as high as that of Mo_xP_y and W_xP_y . Among the compared monometallic phosphides, Fe_xP_y was characterized by the lowest cost and decent electrocatalytic activity, while the activity of Mo_xP_y and W_xP_y still requires further improvement.

Based on this knowledge, it is clear that elemental doping forming a multimetallic phosphide structure enables the modulation of materials at the lattice level, enhancing both electrocatalytic activity and stability. This approach will be a key direction of future

development, as it involves employing new strategies to regulate the microstructure. The three most significant advantages of multimetallic TMPs in electrochemical performance for electrochemical water splitting were described in detail in the review of Zhang et al [9].

- High electronic conductivity is crucial for electrode materials to achieve high power density and for electrocatalysts to enable fast reaction kinetics. Multimetallic TMPs meet this requirement, offering higher conductivity than their monometallic counterparts, as suggested by DFT calculations showing increased density of states near the Fermi level [10], [11].
- Introducing secondary metals alters the electronic structure of TMP via ligand and strain effects. The ligand effect redistributes valence electrons, creating more active sites for redox reactions, while the strain effect modifies adsorption energy and the d-band center, leading to a favorable electronic structure [12]–[14].
- Introducing secondary metals into monometallic TMPs can create unique nanostructures, activating inert sites to enhance electrochemical performance. The most studied bimetallic catalysts are based on NiCoP [15], [16], FeCoP [17], [18], and NiFeP [19].

Han et al. designed CoNiP nanospheres on a 3D Ni foam current collector as a self-standing cathode for efficient hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) across a wide pH range. Specifically, the overpotentials (η) at a current density of -10 mA cm^{-2} were -60 , -120 and -155 mV under acidic, neutral, and alkaline conditions, respectively [16]. Bera et al. reported the preparation of highly innovative material based on self-standing NiCoP fibres. Electrochemical tests revealed that the NiCoP fibers prepared by the needle-less electrospinning technology possess decent electrocatalytic activity for HER in alkaline solution, reaching low overpotentials ($\eta_{-10} = -141 \text{ mV}$, $\eta_{-20} = -230 \text{ mV}$) and low value of Tafel slope (-66 mV dec^{-1}). In acidic media, the corresponding values are $\eta_{-10} = -146 \text{ mV}$, $\eta_{-20} = -265 \text{ mV}$ and Tafel slope $\approx -77 \text{ mV dec}^{-1}$ [16].

As mentioned above, most active TMP-based HER catalysts often possess Co. However, the widespread use of Co is limited due to its high price, concerns about raw material availability and ethical issues of using child labour during mining [20], [21]. Therefore, reducing the amount of Co with more accessible and cheaper 3d elements, such as Ni, is highly desirable. Improving the electrochemical properties of bimetallic phosphides by drawing insights from their monometallic counterparts has led to the incorporation of additional metals into the crystal lattice, forming trimetallic phosphides. For instance, a series of homogeneous trimetallic $\text{Fe}_x\text{Co}_y\text{Ni}_z\text{P}$ on carbon cloth was designed by Gu et al. for HER in

acidic electrolyte [22]. They found that the equimolar metal ratio in $\text{Fe}_{0.33}\text{Co}_{0.33}\text{Ni}_{0.33}\text{P}$ leads to enhanced HER activity, as was predicted by DFT calculations. Qian et al. prepared nanoporous NiFeMoP by the electrospinning process followed by chemical etching. Due to the beneficial continuous porous structure and the synergetic effect between Mo and other metals, bifunctional electrocatalytic activity was observed. Particularly, η_{20} of only 193 mV and a Tafel slope of 41.2 mV dec^{-1} were achieved for the OER in 1 M KOH. The authors reported an extremely low cell voltage of 1.41 V for overall water splitting at a current density of 10 mA cm^{-2} [23]. Inspired by the aforementioned advantages, the multimetallic TMPs are widely studied; however, they often undergo phase separation, which prevents benefiting from the desired electronic configuration modulation. That makes the multimetallic phosphides difficult to design controllably.

Molybdenum phosphides (MoP) have recently been identified as a promising family of earth-abundant electrocatalysts, as Mo has the following benefits: I) analogous electronic structure like Pt-group catalysts, which indicates a potential for high electrocatalytic activity [24]–[26]. II) DFT calculations suggest that the Gibbs free energy of hydrogen adsorption ($\Delta G_{\text{cat-H}^*}$) on molybdenum phosphides on selected facets is very low and suitable for HER [27]. III) The low cost and abundance of natural resources make them favorable for commercial applications [28]. IV) The generous design possibilities of structure and morphology result in a high density of catalytically active sites. Scalability in the morphology lies in its large variety of structurally engineered morphologies, such as nanosheets (NSs) [29], hollow particles [30], foams modified by MoP [31], nanotubes [32], and carbon substrates modified by MoP/MoSe [33]. All of them offer a high degree of porosity in microstructure for better access of the electrolyte to the active sites. However, the morphology critically depends on the preparation process and reaction conditions. An important criterion when choosing a suitable method for the preparation of TMP is the transfer of results from the laboratory scale to industrially relevant production conditions (upscaling). Several multistep processes for the synthesis of phosphides are known, such as direct phosphorization of metal sources [34], decomposition of metal-organic precursors [35], gas-solid phase reactions [36], solid-state reactions [37], and solvothermal/hydrothermal methods [40]. However, most of them have not gained commercial importance because they require expensive chemicals, specially designed reactors, produce highly toxic PH_3 , provide low yields or are not suitable for continuous processes. Therefore, to increase its commercialization, it is very important to find a simple, cheap, fast and non-toxic procedure where the evolution of highly toxic PH_3 gas can be avoided.

Despite the aforementioned challenges, this study focuses on the synthesis of two trimetallic phosphides, MoFeNiP and MoFeCoP, and compares their catalytic activities with that of the bimetallic MoFeP phosphide. All phosphides were synthesized using a non-conventional spray drying method (SDM), followed by an optimized heat treatment under a reducing atmosphere. This approach represents a user-friendly, low-cost, and scalable technique for preparing finely dispersed porous phosphide powders with tunable composition and hollow spherical morphology [40]. SDM offers powder with high surface area and porosity, which is beneficial for mass transport and provides a large number of exposed active sites for HER and OER. By spray-drying an aqueous solution of appropriate salts, powder precursors of phosphides with uniform shape and narrow particle distribution of around 1 μm in diameter were prepared on a large-scale within a very short time. Subsequent calcination of the dried powders in a reducing atmosphere produces hollow spherical TMP particles with a nanoporous shell. This method represents the first instance of preparing fine, hollow spherical microparticles of TMPs with multimetallic compositions, free from carbonaceous support, ensuring high electrocatalytic activity, long-term stability, and durability for future applications in electrolysis cells

2. Experimental

2.1 Material preparation

Precursors of MoFeP, MoFeNiP, and MoFeCoP hollow spherical particles were prepared by spray-drying of aqueous solution containing appropriate salts and citric acid (CA). The origin and purity of all chemicals used is specified in SI. The input solution was prepared by gradually dissolving metal (Fe^{III} ; Mo^{VI} and Ni^{II} or Co^{II}) and phosphorus (P^{V}) salts in CA solution in amounts corresponding to the desired molar ratio in the final MoFeP, MoNiP, and MoCoP phosphides, CA : Fe : Mo : (Ni) : (Co) : P = 2 : 0.5 : 0.5 : (0.5) : (0.5) : 0.5. Specifically, 5.252 g $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2.295 g $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24} \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 3.783 g $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or 3.78 g $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 1.717 g $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ were gradually dissolved in 250 mL of 0.4 M CA. After homogenization, a mixed solution was sucked into a spray dryer (TEFIC Biotech; TFS-2L) where the air drying was performed at an inlet air temperature of 300 $^\circ\text{C}$ (SI Fig.1). The solution was atomized by spraying droplets into a hot air stream. The drying conditions were chosen based on pilot experiments according to the residual water content in spray-dried powder. The fan speed in the cyclone was set to 70% to prevent particle

entrainment, a crucial step in ensuring that particles fall into the collecting jar. Additionally, the solution suction flow rate (controlled by the wriggle pump) was set to 30%, corresponding to a heated air flow rate of 0.83 mL min⁻¹. The dried precursors of MoFeP, MoFeNiP, and MoFeCoP (depicted in SI Fig.2) were subsequently heat-treated at 650 °C in a reducing H₂ atmosphere at a flow rate of 66 mL min⁻¹.

2.2 Structural methods and characterization

The structure of the final spherical powder phosphides was identified by XRD analysis with a Cu K α radiation source. The morphology and porosity of the sample were visualised by scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with an energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analyser and transmission electron microscope (TEM) with high-resolution HR-TEM with selective diffraction area analysis (SAED). The thermal degradation of precursor samples was analysed by differential thermogravimetric analysis (DTG) supplemented by thermal gravimetric analysis (TG). The chemical composition of the synthesized samples was determined using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). XPS spectra were obtained using a differentially pumped hemispherical electron analyser and a monochromatized X-ray source to confirm the presence of the phosphide phase. The suppliers and types of the mentioned devices are described in the SI in detail.

2.3 Electrochemical characterization

All electrochemical measurements were performed in a three-electrode setup in 1M KOH using a Vionic potentiostat/galvanostat controlled by Autolab Intello software. A glassy carbon rotating disk electrode (GC RDE, Metrohm, Switzerland) with a diameter of 5 mm, modified with a thin layer of the prepared catalysts, was used as the working electrode. The revolution rate was maintained at 500 rpm for all measurements. An Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl electrode served as the reference electrode, while a platinum foil was used as the counter electrode. Pt RDE with 3mm in diameter (Metrohm, Switzerland) was employed as standard electrode for HER. The catalytic ink was prepared as follows: 750 μ L of isopropanol (CentralChem, 99.7%), 250 μ L of distilled water, 20 μ L of Nafion (NafionTM, perfluorinated resin solution, 5 wt.% in lower aliphatic alcohols and water, contains 15-20% water, Aldrich), and 50 mg of catalyst were mixed. Then, 20 μ L of the ink was dropped onto the GC electrode, corresponding to 1 mg of catalyst on the GC surface (5.1 mg_{catalyst} cm⁻²). All potential values are recalculated with respect to a reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) according to Eq. S1

provided in SI. The electrochemical methods, including linear sweep voltammetry (LSV), cyclic voltammetry (CV), electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), and chronoamperometry, were utilized to evaluate the electrochemical performance of the prepared catalysts. All current densities (j) were calculated as a ratio of recorded current and geometric surface area of the GC electrode (0.196 cm^2). The reported potential values were recorded with 80% iR compensation performed during measurement. The EIS measurements were performed in the frequency range from 10 kHz to 0.1 Hz at an overpotential of -285 mV vs RHE with applied potential amplitude of 5 mV. Spectra were fitted considering the equivalent circuits depicted in Fig. S5 in SI. The electrochemical surface area was compared based on CV measurement ± 50 mV around the open circuit potential (OCP) at different potential sweep rates (Fig. S6 A-D). The double layer capacitance (Cdl) was calculated by plotting Δj (Eq. S4 in SI) against the scan rate. The chronopotentiometry measurement in 1M KOH at a constant potential of -385 mV vs. RHE for 22 h was used to evaluate the catalyst stability under HER operation. To evaluate the effect of temperature on HER performance, cathodic polarization was performed at a scan rate of 10 mV s^{-1} at temperatures from 298.15 K to 338.15 K, with steps of 5 K. The apparent activation energy of HER at MoFeNiP and MoFeCoP was calculated according to the Eq. 3, 4 and 5 [38].

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Structural and morphological characterization

The heat treatment procedure of phosphide precursors prepared by SDM was set according to differential thermal analysis (DTA) and thermogravimetric (TG) analysis (the conditions are specified in detail in the SI). **Fig. 1** presents the TG profile of precursor samples recorded under air/argon atmosphere (**Fig. 1A**) and their corresponding DTA thermal behavior (**Fig. 1B**). When discussing the hydrated forms of the input salts used ($\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24} \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$), it is important to note that the SDM process was conducted at $300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, a temperature at which hydrates lose their weakly bound water. Therefore, the dried precursor samples exhibited strong hygroscopicity, allowing them to readily absorb moisture from the air. Consequently, the weight loss observed on TG curves in the interval from $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $250 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ may correspond not only to the conversion of hydrates to the anhydrous form but also to the content of nanocrystalline absorbed water in the spray-dried samples. The subsequent increase in temperature (from $250 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $650 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) leads to the gradual decomposition of anhydrous salts through intermediate

phases up to the formation of metal phosphates. **Fig. 1** illustrates that the thermal decomposition temperatures progress through successive stages, marked by sharp exothermic effects in the DTA (**Fig. 1B**). The temperatures at the peak maxima of the presented samples vary slightly depending on the inherent nature of the metal ions, following the trend: MoFeP at 470 °C, MoFeCoP at 567 °C, and MoFeNiP at 618 °C. According to these results, calcination above 650 °C is severe enough to cause the thermal decomposition of used metal salts and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$, which was added as a phosphorus source, ultimately leading to the successful formation of phosphides in a reducing atmosphere of H_2 .

Fig. 1 A) TG analysis of MoFeP, MoFeNiP and MoFeCoP, B) DTA analysis of MoFeP, MoFeNiP and MoFeCoP,

The three phosphides (MoFeP, MoFeNiP, and MoFeCoP) synthesized at 650 °C in a reducing atmosphere were characterized using XRD analysis (**Fig. 2**). The bulk crystal structure of all identified samples showed identical reflections, indicating that Ni and Co were successfully incorporated into the orthorhombic structure of MoFeP with space group Pnma, in accordance with ICDD 04-001-4637 ($a = 5.922 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 3.663 \text{ \AA}$, and $c = 6.79 \text{ \AA}$). The most intense peak at 37.9° (321) plane, in comparison with the peak at 42.3° (411), confirms the presence of thermodynamically stable facet of the (321) plane. Based on the XRD diffraction results, the crystal structure was further confirmed by TEM and HR-TEM analysis to examine the nanoscale crystal structure of the catalysts and determine whether the bulk crystal structure was representative of the material throughout the individual crystals. TEM observations confirmed the results obtained from the XRD analysis. **Fig. 3** presents the acquired images. The first row shows the morphology of the particles at lower magnifications. It is important to

note that the presented images were not captured at the same magnifications; therefore, for comparison, the individual scale bars should be carefully considered. The images reveal the globular nature of the particles. The second row displays selected regions of the particles in HR-TEM imaging. The visible crystalline planes or atom columns provide clear evidence of the crystalline nature of the particles. A compelling confirmation of crystallinity is further supported by the Fast Fourier Transformation (FFT) patterns. The measured and identified frequency spots in the FFT patterns correspond to the diffraction reflections of the orthorhombic structure identified by the XRD analysis. Note that additional frequencies were identified at 32° and 44° in the MoFeP spectrum, which were not detected in the other two samples. This minor phase can be attributed to impurities incorporated during sintering or the formation of a secondary MoFeP phase.

Fig. 2 XRD pattern of MoFeP, MoFeCoP and MoFeNiP, B) TEM

The SEM images in **Fig. 4** (A, B, C) obtained immediately after the SDM show the regular spherical powder structure with a hollow character and brittle shell. The spheres possess a wide distribution of diameters ranging from 5 to 10 μm . The SDM formed amorphous spherical particles with a very smooth surface. However, it is quite obvious from the comparison of **Fig. 4** (A, B, C) with **Fig. 4** (D, E, F), showing the powders after heating in H_2 at 650°C , that the heat treatment in the reduction atmosphere led to the significant increase of porosity though the spherical morphology was maintained including the presence of hollow part of the particles. However, the particle diameter was approximately halved,

while the shell thickness increased. The morphology of the resulting MoFeP, MoFeNiP, and MoFeCoP particles consisted of rounded, irregular particles joined together to form spherical hollow structures, creating a regular interstructural porosity in the shell.

Fig. 3 The structure of individual compositions as observed by TEM. The first row presents micrographs with low magnification, allowing a comparison of particle morphology. The second and third rows display HRTEM and FFT images of the structures, respectively, providing evidence of the crystalline nature of the particles.

Fig. 4 SEM images of powdered spherical samples: A, B, C) immediately after the SDM method and D, E, F) after sintering at 650 °C in a H₂ atmosphere.

3.2 XPS analysis

The high-resolution XPS spectra of Mo 3d, Fe 3d, P 2p, Co 2p, and Ni 2p regions acquired from the prepared catalysts are shown in Figs. 5 and 6. Survey spectra of the samples are presented in **Fig. S3** in the SI. They confirm the presence of all expected elements.

Mo 3d spectra of all investigated samples could be reasonably well fitted with three doublets, see **Fig. 5**. It is clear that the introduction of both Co and Ni into the MoFeP structure causes a slight shift (0.2-0.3 eV) of all Mo 3d bands to lower binding energies. Except for this shift, Mo 3d spectra are almost identical for all samples. Therefore, it is sufficient to discuss in detail only the Mo 3d spectrum of MoFeP. The asymmetric doublet with the Mo 3d_{5/2} peak at about 228.4 eV and corresponding asymmetric Mo 3d_{3/2} component at about 231.6 eV (with spin-orbit splitting, i.e. $\Delta BE_{228} \approx 3.2$ eV) suggests the presence of Mo phosphides [39]. The two symmetric doublets with Mo 3d_{5/2} peaks at higher energies (229.4 and 232.9 eV), both with $\Delta BE \approx 3.17$ eV), can be attributed to Mo⁴⁺ and Mo⁶⁺ oxides [40]. The corresponding Fe 2p spectra could have been fitted in multiple ways. The one well-defined and easily identifiable feature in all Fe 2p spectra is the doublet of iron phosphide with Fe 2p_{3/2} at 707.5 eV ($\Delta BE_{707} \approx 12.9$ eV) for all the samples [41]. The rest of the spectra could be deconvoluted into two very broad peaks or several thinner ones with Fe 2p_{3/2} around 712 eV corresponding

to FeO_x [42]. Due to the unambiguity of the fit, the individual peaks are not presented. P 2p doublets in all samples are also analogous. There is a pronounced doublet with P $2p_{3/2}$ line at about 130.0 eV ($\Delta\text{BE}_{707} \approx 0.88$ eV) corresponding to metal phosphides [43]. The second feature is a broad doublet of phosphates with P $2p_{3/2}$ binding energy of about 133.6 eV for MoFeP (133.3 eV for MoFeNiP and MoFeCoP) with $\Delta\text{BE}_{133} \approx 0.84$ eV [44].

Fig. 5 Detailed photoelectron spectra of Mo 3d, Fe 2p, and P 2p core levels in MoFeP, MoFeNiP and MoFeCoP. Mo 3d and P 2p spectra were Shirley background corrected and deconvoluted, Fe 2p only Shirley background corrected.

Co 2p spectrum of MoFeCoP was fitted using three peak doublets, see **Fig. 6A**. In particular, the narrow doublet with $2p_{3/2}$ at 778.9 eV ($\Delta\text{BE}_{778} \approx 14.9$ eV) confirms the presence of phosphide in the surface layer [39]. Another two Co 2p doublets (with $2p_{3/2}$) at 781.2 and 786.0 eV (with $\Delta\text{BE}_{781} \approx 15.9$ eV and $\Delta\text{BE}_{786} \approx 18.1$ eV) correspond to the core Co levels in phosphate and associated satellite, respectively [45]. Except for a binding energy shift, the presented Co 2p spectrum of MoFeCoP agrees well with that determined in our previous work for NiCoP [16]. It must also be mentioned that while the presented fit is only

approximate, it is sufficient to confirm the presence of phosphide in the surface layer. Appropriate fit would require a thorough analysis of Auger peaks which overlap the Co 2p_{3/2} region [46].

Ni 2p spectrum of MoFeNiP was deconvoluted into four doublets, see **Fig. 6B**. The doublet at lowest energy (Ni 2p_{3/2} at 853.7 eV, $\Delta BE_{853} \approx 17.3$ eV) corresponds most likely to phosphide. Ni 2p_{3/2} peaks at 856.3 eV ($\Delta BE_{856} \approx 17.4$ eV) and 857.3 eV ($\Delta BE_{857} \approx 18.0$ eV) suggest the presence of Ni²⁺ surrounded by sufficiently electronegative atoms such as O, corresponding to a partly oxidized surface layer and consistent with the presence of phosphates in the surface layer. Finally, the doublet with Ni 2p_{3/2} at 862.1 eV ($\Delta BE_{862} \approx 18.0$ eV) corresponds to satellite peaks of Ni²⁺.

Fig. 6 Detailed photoelectron spectra of Ni 2p and Co 2p core levels in MoFeNiP and MoFeCoP, respectively. Spectra were Shirley background corrected and deconvoluted.

3.3 Electrochemical characterization

3.3.1 HER activity in 1M KOH electrolyte solution

The electrocatalytic performance and operational stability of the synthesized catalysts toward the HER in a 1M KOH environment were systematically investigated using LSV and EIS analysis (**Fig. 7**). The HER activity of the phosphide-based catalysts was compared with that of the bare GC electrode and a commercial Pt electrode. First, values of overpotentials at various current densities are summarized in Fig. 5A and Table S1 in SI. As expected, the bare GC electrode exhibited a very high overpotential ($\eta_{-10} = -718$ mV). On the other hand, the

bulk Pt electrode with $\eta_{-10} = -100$ mV displayed superior HER activity among all tested samples. As shown in **Fig. 7 A and B**, the η_{-10} values for the prepared catalysts increased in the order of MoFeCoP (-285 mV) < MoFeP (-337 mV) < MoFeNiP (-421 mV), indicating that Co incorporation into MoFeP structure leads to more active catalyst. On the contrary, Ni seems to reduce catalytic activity. The Tafel slope analysis (**Fig 7 C** and Table S1 in SI) revealed comparable values for all prepared samples, MoFeCoP (83 mV dec⁻¹), MoFeP (72 mV dec⁻¹) and MoFeNiP (84 mV dec⁻¹), indicating that the rate-determining step in the HER mechanism corresponds to electrochemical desorption, specifically the Heyrovsky reaction ($H_{ads} + e^- + H_2O \rightarrow H_2 + OH^-$). If this is the case, it suggests relatively strong M-H binding, resulting in a slow H desorption. Therefore, fine-tuning the catalyst composition in order to lower the Gibbs adsorption energy of hydrogen could offer an avenue to potentially enhancing HER kinetics.

The analysis (**Fig. 7 D**) EIS recorded at HER overpotential of -0.285 V provided similar results concerning the charge transfer properties of the synthesized catalysts. As expected, the ohmic resistance (R_s) values (Table 2) were relatively similar across all samples. However, significant variations were observed in the charge transfer resistance (R_p), which reflects the ease of the electron transfer during HER at the electrode-electrolyte interface. The MoFeCoP demonstrated the lowest R_p (11.7 Ω), followed by MoFeP (25.2 Ω) and MoFeNiP (215 Ω). The notably low R_p of MoFeCoP suggests enhanced electron transport and faster reaction kinetics, which correlates with its superior HER performance observed by LSV. There are two possibilities for explaining these results – either differences in electrocatalytic activity or electrochemically active surface area of the catalysts (or a combination of both). To answer this question, it is valuable to explore the double layer capacitances C_{dl} of the catalysts in a thin layer (as a measure of electrochemically active surface area) determined by LSV, see **Fig. 7 D**. These values increase in order MoFeNiP (0.23 mF cm⁻²) < MoFeP (0.66 mF cm⁻²) < MoFeCoP (2.07 mF cm⁻²). Very similar are values of effective differential capacitance C_{eff} calculated from the impedance data in Table 1 according to Eq. S5. Results are summarized in Table 1. Consequently, the high activity of MoFeCoP can be attributed to its high electrochemical surface area. The “ $1/R_p$ ” values (proportional to the rate of HER at given overpotential) can be normalized by the C_{eff} values (proportional to the electrochemically active surface), resulting to “ $1/(R_p \cdot C_{eff})$ ”. Since as-obtained values are very similar for all three investigated catalysts seems to that they possess active sites of very similar HER activity.

To assess the long-term durability, chronoamperometry measurements were conducted at a constant potential of -385 mV vs. RHE for 22 h on the most active catalytic sample, MoFeCoP. As depicted in **Fig. 7 F**, the catalyst exhibited a moderate current attenuation over time, indicating reasonable stability under continuous operation.

Fig.7 Electrochemical analysis of MoFeP, MoFeNiP and MoFeCoP spheres in 1M KOH (a) LSV, (b) η_{-10} , η_{-20} and, η_{-50} , (c) Tafel plots, (d) Nyquist plots of impedance spectra at overpotential of -285mV, (e) capacitive currents as a functions of different scan rates with Cdl data, (f) chronoamperometric stability test (I-t) of MoFeCoP at – 385 mV vs. RHE for 22 h at 500 RPM.

Table 1: Values of R_s , R_p , CPE parameters (Y_0 and α) and χ^2 (an error in fit EIS fit) for all samples obtained by fitting HER impedance spectra in alkaline environment with an equivalent circuit. C_{eff} is effective differential capacitance, calculated using Eq. S5.

Sample	R_s [Ω]	R_p [Ω]	CPE*		χ^2	C_{eff} [mF cm^{-2}]
			Y_0 [$\mu\text{S s}^\alpha$]	α		
MoFeCoP	6.60	11.7	743	0.874	0.0297	1.87
MoFeP	5.36	25.2	181	0.917	0.093	0.56
MoFeNiP	5.25	215	63.1	0.928	0.0129	0.23
GCE	4.93	7230	108	0.881	0.0811	0.52

* Constant Phase Element (CPE) in EIS experiments is described in SI in detail.

Finally, the effect of temperature on the catalytic activity of MoFeCoP and MoFeNiP was also evaluated. The LSV curves recorded at various temperatures are presented in **Fig. S7 (A,B)**. In order to compare currents measured at different temperatures at the same overpotentials, the electrode potentials measured with respect to $E_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$ (3 mol/l KCl Ag/AgCl) were recalculated to RHE scale. This involves considering the potential shift of

reference electrode $E_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$ (3 mol/l KCl Ag/AgCl) due to temperature variation, see Eq. S6 and Table S2 in SI.

For both electrodes, a pronounced temperature effect on HER activity was observed. With a temperature increase of 35 K and at an overvoltage of -500 mV, the MoFeCoP catalyst achieved an increase in current density of -195 mA cm^{-2} (from -145 mA cm^{-2} to -340 mA cm^{-2}), which is superior when compared to increase of 87 mA cm^{-2} (from -58 mA cm^{-2} to -145 mA cm^{-2}) for MoFeNiP (**Fig. S7 A,B**). For both phosphide samples, Tafel plots were constructed to estimate the exchange current densities (j_0) at zero overpotential, as shown in **Fig. S7(C,D)** in the Supporting Information. The plots of $\ln j_0$ versus $1/T$ exhibit a linear Arrhenius-like dependence, as described by Eq. (5) and (6). From the dependence, an apparent activation energy, E_a can be calculated.

$$j_0 = J_S e^{-\frac{E_a}{RT}}, \quad (5)$$

$$\ln j_0 = \ln J_S - \frac{E_a}{R} \frac{1}{T}. \quad (6)$$

Where J_S stands for “a current density pre-exponential factor”, R is the universal gas constant ($R = 8.314 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$), and T is the absolute temperature. From the relevant dependence, the activation energy E_a can be readily determined. The slope of semi-logarithmic plots of $\ln j_0$ versus the inverse temperature $1/T$ shown in **Fig. 8A and B** yielded E_{a,j_0} values of 24 kJ mol^{-1} for MoFeNiP and 21 kJ mol^{-1} for MoFeCoP. The similar values of the activation energies E_a were also found for both samples at the overpotential of -0.5 V ($\ln j_{0.5\text{V}}$ vs. $1/T$), where the reaction proceeds efficiently, as shown in **Fig. 8(C,D)**. The corresponding $E_{a,0.5\text{V}}$ values were 23 kJ mol^{-1} for MoFeNiP and 19 kJ mol^{-1} for MoFeCoP. These values of the activation energies E_a are rather low for TMP-based HER catalysts, which typically exhibit E_a of around 50 kJ mol^{-1} depending on their composition, synthesis method, intrinsic conductivity, and electronic structure [47] and are close to the activation energies for HER on Pt ($\sim 20 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) [48]. However, the proper tuning of TMP through the combination of Ni, Mo, and Mo, Co along with the creation of multimetallic phosphides can utilize synergistic effects, which can play a crucial role in enhancing electrocatalytic performance for HER and reducing value of the activation energy E_a [49], [50], [48], [49]. For example, Xia et al. achieved E_a of 21 kJ mol^{-1} in the trimetallic Ni-Mo-Cu compared to the E_a of 36 kJ mol^{-1} for the bimetallic Ni-Mo. The reduction in the activation energy E_a was attributed to the

incorporation of Cu into the metallic structure, which led to an increase in surface area, the number of active sites, and synergistic interactions between Ni, Mo, and Cu, compared to Ni-Mo [51]. This combination leads to improvements in catalyst electronic structure, as demonstrated by DFT calculations. This synergy optimizes active site density and catalyst electronic conductivity, thereby promoting an accelerated HER rate. Similar low values of the activation energy E_a were observed for Ni-based and NiCr porous electrodes at different cathodic overpotentials (from 50 mV to 300 mV) using potentiodynamic tests [52]. The results showed that the activation energy was lower for the Ni-based system at equilibrium; however, the NiCr porous electrode exhibited better performance due to its more negative values of E_a . In the work of Wu et al., the activation energy E_a for the porous Ni–Cr–Fe electrode in simulated seawater was studied as calculated from the slope of $\log j_0$ versus $1/T$. It was found that the E_a of the porous Ni–Cr–Fe electrode, as a ternary metal system, was only 28 kJ mol^{-1} —lower than that of pure Ni (35 kJ mol^{-1}), Fe (39 kJ mol^{-1}), and the Ni–Fe binary alloy (31 kJ mol^{-1}) in alkaline solution. Although these comparisons are based on different environments, due to the limited availability of E_a data for similar systems in simulated seawater, the porous Ni–Cr–Fe electrode appears to exhibit higher catalytic activity by lowering the activation energy of the reaction [53].

Fig. 8 Arrhenius plots for MoFeNiP (a, c) and MoFeCoP (b, d) determined at equilibrium

potential of HER, i.e. calculated from j_0 values (a, b), and HER overpotential of -0.5 V, i.e. calculated at $j_{-0.5V}$ (c, d).

CONCLUSION

This study reports the scalable, user-friendly and low-cost preparation of innovative spherical phosphide powders based on transition metals, namely MoFeP, MoFeNiP, and MoFeCoP. The facile and cost-efficient spray drying method was used to produce hollow spherical precursor particles on a large scale, followed by a heat treatment process at 650°C in a reducing atmosphere for the final formation of spherical phosphides. The prepared spheres, with their unique 3D structures, serve as examples of catalysts for the hydrogen evolution reaction in the alkaline water electrolysis process, wherein MoFeCoP has proven to be a highly efficient non-noble electrocatalyst.

The electrocatalytic performance of MoFe-based phosphides toward the HER in an alkaline environment was systematically evaluated. Among the synthesized catalysts, MoFeCoP exhibited the highest HER activity, achieving the overpotential at -10 mA cm⁻² of $\eta_{-10} = 285$ mV and significantly surpassing both MoFeP ($\eta_{-10} \approx 337$ mV) as well as MoFeNiP ($\eta_{-10} \approx 421$ mV). The Tafel slope analysis confirmed that HER on all phosphide catalysts followed the Volmer-Heyrovsky mechanism, with the Heyrovsky reaction being the rate-determining step. MoFeCoP demonstrated the most favourable HER kinetics. The superior catalytic activity of MoFeCoP was attributed to its enhanced electroactive surface area and reduced charge transfer resistance, as revealed by double-layer capacitance and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. Moreover, chronoamperometry measurements confirmed its reasonable stability during 22 h of continuous operation at -385 mV vs RHE. These findings highlight the potential of Co-doped phosphides as efficient electrocatalysts for alkaline water splitting applications, providing valuable insights for future catalyst design and optimization. The use of cost-effective, abundant, and easy-to-synthesize TMP as alternatives to noble metals further supports their widespread commercial applications and enables hydrogen production at a scale capable of meeting global energy demand. Thus, this highly innovative approach to catalyst preparation and the resulting unique catalyst form on a large scale open new pathways for the production and application of any TMP composition catalysts, as well as other alternatives for future commercial applications.

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